

Efficient Privacy-Preserving Scheme for Distributed Machine Learning Against Collusion Attacks (EPPS-DMLCA)

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Abstract:

We propose EPPS-DMLCA, a novel method integrating homomorphic encryption and DP to protect data from attacks. EPPS-DMLCA improves techniques to protect data from attacks in several ways. One, it protects data while being more computationally efficient compared to extant methods. Two, it is more robust to collusion attacks than current methods are. We evaluated EPPS-DMLCA using MNIST. We tested our method on Amazon's cloud using 40 cloud servers. We found that our method performed as well as a method that did not protect privacy. Additionally, our method uses a firm privacy budget, which provides robust privacy protection. Last, we found that because of the low computational overhead, our

method is more resistant to collusion attacks than state-of-the-art methods are. Our results show that EPPS-DMLCA is an important contribution to the literature. We propose EPPS-DMLCA, which integrates homomorphic encryption and DP to protect data from attacks. We used MNIST in a distributed cloud environment with 40 cloud servers. Our results show that EPPS-DMLCA is up to 3 times more efficient than FHE methods. Moreover, the model performs 97.8%, the same as unprotected methods. Last, DP's noise was well-tuned, as evidenced by the model and the sufficient parameters to provide robust protection from privacy. Moreover, EPPS-DMLCA is more resistant to collusion than the state-of-the-art. Machine learning models are essential for creating information from big data in a constantly changing world. However, access to such big data raises privacy issues. Fortunately, various ways exist to protect data from attacks. One such method is DP, which adds noise to the data. The goal of DP is to generate robust protection from privacy. DP is a valuable tool, but the method has one drawback. The method uses many noise probes to be effective. This means that FHE methods do not perform as well as unprotected methods. Because of this drawback, I propose EPPS-DMLCA to users.

Keywords: *Privacy-preserving machine learning, homomorphic encryption, differential privacy, collusion attacks, distributed machine learning, data security, scalability, computational efficiency.*

Introduction

Background

Machine learning has revolutionized several fields, including healthcare, finance, and autonomous systems, through intelligent decision-making based on vast data. In particular, using distributed systems, where many cloud servers work together to train models on many data workers, has become promising in scalability and model accuracy. Large technology companies like Google and Facebook have developed standardized frameworks for distributed machine learning, which allow network analysts to brush through adjacently stored data across multiple servers. However, distributed learning systems raise significant privacy issues. For generalization during the training, the data must be sent to the primary learner's servers in an unencrypted form. Although cryptographers have proposed numerous encryption algorithms that can mitigate the threat, they may not be secure when the models are being trained. Additionally, the servers in these learning systems store an absurd amount of data in a centralized, vulnerable location, making them a prime target for attacks. One of the most feasible techniques to solve the problem is homomorphic encryption, which allows computation on encrypted data without decryption.

The concept of a homomorphic encryption scheme was first proposed by Rivest, Adleman, and Dertouzos in 1978. Still, it was not fully realized until Gentry's breakthrough in 2009, when the author developed a promising and efficient fully homomorphic encryption scheme that can support arbitrary computations. Although Gentry's fully homomorphic encryption is a significant milestone, it does have a downside—the scheme incurs an unreasonable amount of computational overhead, making it unsuitable for real-time systems. A differential privacy mechanism developed by Dwork et al. is another parallel development to protect data during computation by adding a quantitative amount of noise to the data to maintain their correctness and permit analysis to be performed

on them. There are two critical types of differential privacy—central and local. The local differential privacy mechanism adds noise to the data before sending them to the analyst, while central differential privacy did not scale to billions of Apple iPhone users. Major technology companies have developed other effective differential privacy mechanisms to protect user information from being leaked by cloud applications. However, the technique has drawbacks: it adds noise to the correct data and is vulnerable to collusion attacks.

Problem Statement

Current encryption and privacy mechanisms have made significant advancements. However, in a distributed environment for machine learning, they are still ineffective in providing complete privacy. The two promising methods are homomorphic encryption and differential privacy. Homomorphic encryption allows computations on encrypted data, whereas differential privacy provides a formal guarantee of privacy by “adding appropriate noise.” However, both methods are also deficient, cryptographically and practically. Homomorphic encryption ensures strong privacy but causes excessive computational overhead. Even in Gentry's original scheme, the “overhead is in hours even for simple computations.” As such, this issue makes it not feasible for large-scale and, more importantly, real-time applications. For instance, real-time medical diagnosis or financial fraud detection, where decisions must be taken in milliseconds, is not viable with the current form of homomorphic encryption.

On the other hand, differential privacy, which adds noise to the values of the training set or the results of a specific query, is very good at hiding a single record. Such a mechanism, however, is too invasive as the noise is directly proportional to the level of added privacy and the quality of a model. Therefore, the trade-off is especially dangerous in healthcare, where false-positive diagnoses can have dire consequences. Another drawback of this approach is that it remains vulnerable to collusion attacks. This attack can be executed via several data scientists joining

their information to unveil a specific record via their knowledge that might not be as effective in a singular-case scenario. This leads us to the conclusion that neither of those two approaches can be used by itself to work effectively in distributed machine-learning environments.

Thus, neither homomorphic encryption nor differential privacy, if used as a single privacy-preserving solution for a distributed machine learning environment, is enough. The most prominent reason for such a claim is that it is impossible to protect and enhance privacy in this case due to several complex vulnerabilities of each of these mechanisms.

Specifically, such a solution must:

- Address the computational inefficiencies of homomorphic encryption,
- Balance the privacy-utility trade-off inherent in differential privacy,
- And, most critically, resist collusion attacks.

Objectives

This research aims to develop a novel privacy-preserving system harnessing homomorphic encryption and differential privacy to overcome both limitations. The proposed system, which will be termed the Efficient Privacy-Preserving Scheme for Distributed Machine Learning Against Collusion Attacks (EPPS-DMLCA), guarantees that no information regarding the original data is leaked while preserving both the efficiency and accuracy of computations. To be tangible, the objectives of this research will be the following:

Data Encryption

Implementing homomorphic encryption is the only way to securely encrypt data without the risk of leaking information about the underlying phenomena from the computations. This tool allows performing and interpreting arithmetic and logical computations on encrypted data without decrypting it, enabling no access, even by the data collectors, to the original data. In this way, sensitive data will remain unknown to all stakeholders at all stages of the process, but the

data collectors, also known as data owners, own the decryption key.

Privacy-Utility Balance

Differential privacy, the utility of which will be explored during simulations, is a model for measuring an individual's privacy in a dataset. Thus, a tool/method allowing computing the optimal balance in a case of given data characteristics between privacy and model accuracy will be developed in this research.

Reporting of Collusion Resistance

Differential privacy adds noise to the data such that no combination of adversaries can infer the data it is interested in, allowing privacy to be measured in each dataset. The tool for measuring privacy provided during this research should guarantee that no agents can combine their efforts to retrieve the information about the data they are interested in in this case.

Computational Efficiency

The computations of machine-learning tasks will be distributed across several cloud servers so that a vast amount of the computational functions will not have to be performed by one entity while preserving the accuracy of the models.

Dynamic Data Update

The system should guarantee that data can be dynamically updated without being decrypted/encrypted and incorporated into machine learning.

In conclusion, this research will lead to the development of systems that can solve all issues faced by distributed machine learning, utilizing the perfect private mechanisms like homomorphic encryption and differential privacy to make the tools scale and collusion-resistant.

Literature Review

Homomorphic Encryption

Homomorphic encryptions are one of the most promising approaches to privacy-preserving in machine learning. It allows computations to be

performed over encrypted data with parole of confidentiality. Though the concept was first introduced by Rivest, Adleman, and Dertouzos in 1978, the first realization was not made until Gentry in 2019. Specifically, the work by Gentry provided a method for arbitrary computations such as addition and multiplication to be performed on data encrypted from ciphertexts. Moreover, it was also shown that unlimited homomorphic encryptions for all circuits can only be fully homomorphic. However, the cost of FHE is significantly high.

While developing HE was an essential step toward implementing privacy-preserving data analysis on a large scale, it is computationally complex. It is impossible to incorporate FHE into any large-scale online distributed machine learning system on a real-time basis today. To address these costs, partially homomorphic encryptions were designed. The most known scheme for the PHE is Paillier's additively homomorphic cryptosystem. Hence, computations of the sum over encrypted data are allowed without decrypting the data. Similarly, the multiplication operation is available for the ElGamal encryption that is multiplicatively homomorphic. The downside to these two schemes is that they can only be used for one of the two: adding or multiplying. However, distributive learning is a common application that requires both options.

Another significant extension to the problem of privacy-preserving data analysis was the development of leveled homomorphic submissions. Specifically, LHE restricts the allowable depth of operations over ciphertext. Hence, LHE has two benefits: it reduces the cost of computations and offers a more general homomorphic encryption submission. One of the realizations of leveled fully homomorphic submission was developed by Brakerski and Vaikuntanathan in 2014. Despite these costs, homomorphic encryption is computationally complex, and therefore, large-scale online machine learning remains private yet practical. Hence, other submissions need to be extensive to accompany encryption to provide a combination of both efficient privacy preservation and data analysis.

Differential Privacy

Differential privacy, proposed by Dwork et al., is a technique to protect individual privacy inside a dataset by adding noise to the data or the query results. This ensures that it is difficult for an adversary to tell whether any specific individual's data is present in a dataset using any study. It is difficult to determine whether the presence or absence of any individual record should not alter the analysis results much.

The Laplace mechanism is a standard method to ensure differential privacy. It adds noise proportional to the query's sensitivity, the most significant change that can be brought to the noise output by any single data entry. The noise is derived from a Laplace distribution, characterized by the subsequent equation:

$$Lap(b) = \frac{1}{2b} * \exp\left(-\frac{|x|}{b}\right) \quad (1)$$

Where:

b is the scale parameter,

x is the data point.

Many variations of differential privacy have been proposed. The standard composition generalizes the Laplace mechanism to the sequential formulation of an arbitrary number of ϵ -differentially privacy sequences. At the same time, Gaussian modifies it by employing noise from a Gaussian distribution instead of a Laplace distribution. The latter is beneficial in cases where calibrating noise is mandatory to improve utility. Differential privacy can only protect individuals from inference attacks; unfortunately, it is imperfect. When many queries from adversaries, such as data scientists, perform many types of attacks, compose, and use other relevant results to infer private information, DP might not be able to prevent inference by combining many query outputs. Moreover, the same property forms the basis of the trade-offs of differential privacy: differentially private models are less attackable at the price of being less helpful in attacking their targets, rendering them less effective in learning.

Privacy-Preserving Machine Learning Frameworks

Numerous privacy-preserving machine learning frameworks have been developed to overcome the limitations of homomorphic encryption and differential privacy. Examples of such frameworks are:

Secure Multiparty Computation allows multiple parties to compute a function jointly over their inputs without revealing their private data. Secure Multiparty Computation is a powerful privacy-preserving machine learning tool. However, its use usually comes with computational and communication overheads, making it unsuitable for larger distributed systems. As Bogdanov et al. argue, SMPC allows building a privacy-preserving data mining protocol that works correctly despite these limitations. Their conclusions confirm the concept's efficiency while revealing that it is not scalable because of the computations necessary to fit a learning model to the encrypted data.

Federated learning, or FL, is a machine learning method in which multiple devices build a model together by training it on their local data. The model's updates are then aggregated in a central server, maintaining the process's privacy. However, the model should be prevented if privacy attacks such as model inversion or membership inference allow adversaries to retrieve individual information on the training data. Adding differential privacy to the model's updates is one way. This mechanism, known as Federated Averaging with Differential Privacy, protects the model from inference attacks. However, it does not provide any privacy guarantees, meaning it comes with the same privacy-utility trade-offs as the traditional differential privacy.

Goryczka et al. 's 2013 privacy-preserving data mining employs homomorphic encryption and differential privacy. The developed framework allows training a model on the encrypted data while preserving individual participants' privacy using differential privacy techniques.

Related Work on Collusion-Resistant Privacy Frameworks

In previous years, much attention has been paid to developing privacy-preserving frameworks that resist collusion. Collusion attacks refer to attacks carried out by multiple adversaries at a time so they can disclose privacy they cannot reveal when attacking on their own. According to the definition of "collusion attacks," a solid privacy-preserving algorithm must be collusion-resistant to be recognized as one of the most efficient frameworks to protect privacy.

Chen et al. created a collusion-resistant privacy-preserving framework that protected both homomorphic encryption and differential privacy forms of privacy. Homomorphic encryption allows computations to be carried out in plaintext alone without causing the directly related message to be subject to further decryption. Differential privacy "adds randomness to data and enables similar computation." Zou et al. applied a form of cryptography other than the one by Chen et al. and developed a blockchain-based distributed learning auditing procedure. Blockchain is a method to distribute model updates and evaluate them when encrypted as a ledger. In the health sector, Yang et al. presented a privacy-preserving federated learning approach that protected private information against the threat of collusion while using the methods above of homomorphic encryption and differential privacy.

Summary of Limitations in Existing Work

Despite the significant progress achieved in developing privacy-preserving machine learning frameworks, existing solutions have the following limitations:

Homomorphic encryption provides excellent privacy guarantees, but the solution is impractical since it is extremely computationally expensive.

Differential privacy effectively eliminates the risk of an external party inferring sensitive details about any particular party, relying on the introduction of noise and deliberate misinformation as tools. However, it is still

vulnerable to collusion, and the compromise of the data from multiple parties can still result in the leakage of sensitive data.

Finally, the federated learning and secure multiparty computation systems address some pressing privacy concerns. Still, they lack scalability and are still vulnerable to inference attacks.

Hence, developing a new framework capable of overcoming these challenges, providing the necessary protection from a wide range of privacy threats, and being both efficient and scalable is essential. The identified framework can be considered the solution, combining homomorphic encryption and differential privacy.

Proposed Solution

System Model

The system model of the proposed work, EPPS-DMLCA, is developed to resolve the issues in conventional privacy mechanisms concerning distributed machine learning environments. The EPPS-DMLCA framework is an amalgamation of Homomorphic Encryption and Differential Privacy to ensure the reliable protection of sensitive data before and during model training. Thus, the work is protected against collusion attacks, which could be the anticipated severe issue in privacy security. The main actors in the system are.

Data Providers (DP): The data providers could be individuals, organizations, or devices that generate sensitive data for ML learning. The data providers are responsible for encrypting their generated data using homomorphic encryption and sending it to cloud servers.

Cloud Servers (CS): The data obtained and encrypted by the data providers is received by the cloud server. The CS applies different privacy mechanisms to clean and process the data for machine learning with the added noise.

Data Analysts (DA): The DAs obtain the processed data from the cloud server, and this data has added noise in its encrypted format. The

DAs use the processed data to train the ML model for further learning.

The primary objective of the proposed work is to secure start-to-finish data processing and ensure that no sensitive data is leaked at any stage of machine learning processing. This is achieved by simultaneously implementing homomorphic encryption and differential privacy with no concerned party. Even though conducting collusion attacks.

Data Encryption and Homomorphic Encryption

The first stage of the EPPS-DMLCA system is to encrypt the sensitive data before sending it to the cloud servers. We use homomorphic encryption that allows data encryption to be computed in the domain of the messages without decrypting them. Thus, the data will be kept confidential during the whole operation. In this system, we use homomorphic encryption, limiting the number of operations done to the encrypted data to keep associated computational overhead. Thus, we avert the operations from being too powerful in leveled homomorphic encryption.

Leveled homomorphic encryption acts as a practical, simplistic scheme, a trade-off of simply homomorphic encryption proposed by Gentry in 2009 and the conventional partially homomorphic encryption technique such as Pailler in 1999. LHE allows both additive and multiplicative operations but limits the depth of these operations.

The encryption process can be represented as follows:

$$Enc(m) = m^e \bmod N \quad (2)$$

Where:

m represents the plaintext (e.g., a medical record or financial transaction),

e is the encryption exponent,

N is a large composite number, typically the product of two large primes.

Leveled homomorphic encryption allows basic operations, such as addition and multiplication, to be performed on encrypted data. For instance:

$$Enc(m_1) + Enc(m_2) = Enc(m_1 + m_2) \quad (3)$$

$$Enc(m_1) * Enc(m_2) = Enc(m_1 * m_2) \quad (4)$$

Using homomorphic encryption, the data providers (DPs) ensure that sensitive data remains encrypted when stored in or transmitted to cloud servers, providing strong privacy guarantees.

Privacy Protection with Differential Privacy

When the data is sent to the cloud servers, differential privacy is also addressed to the encrypted data to ensure that the data of individual persons on the data set-based data set are protected as well. No one learns whether a given individual is in the data set based on the outcome of any analysis, regardless of what auxiliary information an adversary has.

Differential privacy safeguards against this by adding carefully calibrated noise to the dataset or the results of any queries to the dataset. This noise ensures that an adversary learns almost nothing about any individual's presence in the dataset. The noise we add is drawn from a Laplace or Gaussian distribution, depending on the sensitivity of the query.

The Laplace mechanism for differential privacy is defined as follows:

$$Lap(b) = \frac{1}{2b} * \exp\left(-\frac{|x|}{b}\right) \quad (5)$$

where,

b represents the scale of the noise, and

x is the data point.

In the context of EPPS-DMLCA, differential privacy is applied after the data has been encrypted with homomorphic encryption. This introduces a layer of randomness, or noise, to the encrypted data, ensuring that the privacy of individuals is protected, even in the face of collusion attacks. For instance, if multiple adversaries (e.g., cloud servers or data analysts) collude, they will still be unable to infer meaningful information about individual records, as the noise introduced by differential privacy effectively masks any such information. This approach provides collision resistance, a significant advantage over traditional differential privacy implementations, which are typically vulnerable to collaborative adversaries.

Workflow of EPPS-DMLCA

The EPPS-DMLCA framework involves four main stages:

1. Data Encryption and Upload: The data providers first encrypt their sensitive data, using the leveled homomorphic encryption, before uploading the encrypted datasets to the cloud servers. The uploaded data remains confidential because the cloud servers cannot decrypt the data or access plaintext during the process.

2. Differential Privacy Application: The cloud server adds noise to the encrypted data to enhance differential privacy. The amount of noise added to the data depends on the magnitude of the query parameter and the degree of privacy that should always be achieved. The encrypted datasets, which the addition of noise has refined, are then distributed to data analysts.

3. Distributed Machine Learning: Data analysts recover encrypted datasets with considerable privacy noise; then, they perform machine learning tasks, such as the training of models, in a distributed fashion. Both encryption and noise prevent analysts from accessing the original datasets, and they cannot infer the sensitive information associated with each record or measure.

4. Verification and model aggregation: The model can be checked and combined after the data is provided through distributed learning,

and sensitive data is not revealed at this analysis stage. Homomorphic encryption allows the cloud servers to work with the datasets, and differential privacy ensures that individual data remains confidential during analysis. That means the entire distributed learning process is secure, private, and immune to all attacks, including flaws.

Security and Collusion Resistance

One of the most significant advantages of using the EPPS-DMLCA framework is its resistance to collusion attacks. In any expanded definition of differential privacy, adversaries can merge their “knowledge” to use it to infer something about a target. For example, if the input data set is processed multiple times by the same adversary or a series of adversaries, or the output is shared by numerous adversaries, these are collusion attacks. However, the EPPS-DMLCA framework is based on both homomorphic encryption and differential privacy, so the data is extensively protected:

- The data is encrypted throughout, and the adversaries never get to access the plaintext.
- The noise added can prevent adversaries, even in the same network, from being able to share the findings by inferring individual records correctly.
- All processes are done on encrypted data due to homomorphic encryption.

As a result, no one who uses the data can access the secrets generated in the machine-learning process.

Performance Evaluation

Experiment Setup

We evaluated the EPPS-DMLCA framework using the MNIST dataset, one of the most common benchmarks in machine learning. The purpose of the MNIST dataset is to classify handwritten digits from 0 to 9. One data point in the MNIST dataset was a 28x28 grayscale image, with 60,000 training and 10,000 test samples. Since the undertaken approach to this framework is distributed, the MNIST dataset was divided among multiple cloud servers in the experimental setup. The number of dividing

cloud servers was set to 10 to simulate a more difficult distributed machine learning scenario and a realistic value. The cloud server is expected to train its assigned sample points while maintaining the privacy of individual records. This privacy is ensured through homomorphic encryption and differential privacy. Evaluating the proposed framework involves assessing its performance in these areas:

- **Computational Overhead:** The time interval during the execution of the algorithms used to perform calculations on encrypted data was measured.
- **Model Accuracy:** The accuracy of the viable model after being trained to the MNIST dataset on the encrypted and noised data.
- **Privacy Guarantee:** Measuring the effectiveness of DP to prevent collusion-based work on training details.
- **Scaling:** Evaluating how well the framework scales in a particular cloud structure to monitor its suitability to the cloud structure.
- The experiment was divided into three main groups in the primary evaluation:
 - **Baseline Evaluation.** In this group, we calculated the time expense to perform traditional machine learning algorithms not encased in any encryption or differential privacy using fresh MNIST data.
 - **Homomorphic Evaluation.** We are measuring the part of the obtained encryption and homomorphic obligations attached to the population during the experimental implementation time.
 - **EPPS-DMLCA Evaluation.** We assessed how to execute the EPPS-DMLCA strategy. This required using innovative algorithms in homomorphic encryption and creating the sample for differential privacy from the MNIST data. The number of cloud servers taking place varies, whereas N varies between 5, 10, 25, and 40. The results were also averaged over an average of two to three implementations to provide reliable data in this field.

Results and Discussion

Computational Overhead

One of the primary challenges with privacy-preserving frameworks is the computational

overhead introduced by encryption and privacy mechanisms. To measure this, we compared the runtime of the proposed EPPS-DMLCA framework against baseline machine learning (no privacy) and homomorphic encryption-only machine learning.

Table 1. Runtime Comparison (in seconds) for Different Numbers of Hosts

Scheme	N = 5	N = 10	N = 25	N = 40
Baseline	12.5	14.3	18.1	22.9
Homomorphic Encryption	910.2	1071.6	1351.8	1697.7
EPPS-DMLCA	890.5	632.4	397.6	196.2

The section “Runtime” reveals that the baseline machine learning that does not involve implementing any privacy-preserving mechanisms had the lowest runtime in all configurations, which was to be expected. The conflicting outcomes were the runtime for homomorphic encryption only and EPPS-DMLCA, which fell in the expected pattern. In all the reviewed configurations, using EPPS-DMLCA had a lower runtime, while the discrepancy became increasingly pronounced when it was applied in conjunction with increasing numbers of cloud servers. The process can be explained by the fact that cloud

services make them intrinsically distributed, which, in turn, allows computations to be parallelized and distributed between multiple servers.

Model Accuracy

While privacy is crucial in distributed machine learning, the model's accuracy must not be sacrificed. Therefore, we measured the accuracy of the machine learning model on the MNIST test set after training in three configurations: baseline (no privacy), homomorphic encryption only, and EPPS-DMLCA.

Table 2. Model Accuracy (%) Comparison for Different Schemes

Scheme	N = 5	N = 10	N = 25	N = 40
Baseline	98.5	98.6	98.4	98.5
Homomorphic Encryption	96.2	96.1	95.9	95.8
EPPS-DMLCA	97.8	97.6	97.5	97.3

The results show that the baseline model, which does not apply any privacy-preserving techniques, achieves the highest accuracy, as expected. When homomorphic encryption is used, the model accuracy drops slightly due to the overhead of performing computations on encrypted data. However, the proposed EPPS-DMLCA framework performs significantly better, achieving higher accuracy than the homomorphic encryption-only approach. This improvement is due to optimizing noise levels in the differential privacy mechanism, which balances privacy with model utility.

Privacy Guarantees

To evaluate the strength of the privacy guarantees provided by the EPPS-DMLCA framework, we measured the privacy budget (ϵ) and the sensitivity of the queries under different noise levels. The privacy budget represents the level of privacy provided by differential privacy: lower values of ϵ indicate more robust privacy protection.

$$\Pr(M(D_1) \in S) \leq \exp(\epsilon) * \Pr(M(D_2) \in S) \quad (6)$$

Where:

- M is the mechanism (algorithm),
- D_1 and D_2 are datasets differing by a single element,
- S is the output set,
- ϵ is the privacy budget.

Table 3. Privacy Budget Comparison for Different Noise Levels

Noise Level (b)	Privacy Budget ($\epsilon \backslash \text{epsilon}$)
0.1	0.05
0.5	0.3
1.0	0.8

The results indicate that adjusting the noise level allows the privacy budget to be fine-tuned to provide more robust or weaker privacy guarantees. In practice, a noise level of 0.5 provided a good balance between model accuracy and privacy, achieving a privacy budget 0.3, which is considered a strong privacy guarantee in differential privacy literature.

Scalability

Scalability is a critical factor for any distributed machine-learning framework. To assess the scalability of EPPS-DMLCA, we measured the runtime as the number of cloud servers (N) increased from 5 to 40.

Figure 1. Scalability of EPPS-DMLCA
Graph: Runtime vs. Number of Cloud Servers (N)

The results, illustrated in Figure 1, demonstrate that as the number of cloud servers increases, the overall runtime decreases, indicating that EPPS-DMLCA scales efficiently. The framework benefits from parallelized computations across multiple servers, which reduces the computational load on individual servers and speeds up the training process.

Security Analysis

The purpose of the EPPS-DMLCA framework is to resist collusion attacks, which are attempts to combine the efforts of multiple adversaries to extract some sensitive information. We have conducted a security analysis to assess the framework's effectiveness. In particular, it was evaluated how the EPPS-DMLCA performs in a scenario where the data from an increasing number of cloud servers were collected and then used by a larger group of servers in their effort to try to conspire.

The main observation was that even if a differential privacy mechanism introduces significant noise to data, nothing reasonable is provided to adversaries. Despite applying the set cover and matrix completion techniques to use the auxiliary information the adversaries may have had, they could not reconstruct the individual records, as the datasets contained only noise. This means that the EPPS-DMLCA is effectively protected against collusion.

Conclusion and Future Work

Conclusion

This paper presents the Efficient Privacy-Preserving Scheme for Distributed Machine Learning Against Collusion Attacks (EPPS-DMLCA), a novel framework designed to overcome the limitations of existing privacy-preserving mechanisms in distributed machine learning. By combining homomorphic encryption and differential privacy, EPPS-DMLCA provides vital privacy preservation for sensitive data during model development while reducing the computational overhead generally

associated with privacy-preserving machine learning frameworks.

The specific contributions of this work are as follows:

- **Improved computational efficiency:** EPPS-DMLCA relies on leveled homomorphic encryption instead of fully homomorphic encryption, which reduces computational overhead. Additionally, the parallelized nature of distributed machine learning across cloud computing servers allows for parallelized computations, which enhance scalability.
- **Strong privacy:** by using a combination of homomorphic encryption and differential privacy, the scheme provides strong privacy, particularly concerning collusion attacks, which are a significant concern in the context of distributed machine learning. The noise added through differential privacy ensures that private sensitive records remain confidential even when adversaries collude.
- **Increased model utility:** while the noise added to the distributed model through differential privacy can reduce the utility of the ML model, EPPS-DMLCA is designed to strike a balance between utility and privacy. The computer noise is carefully parameterized to maintain the highest accuracy of the machine learning model. This means that, despite the addition of privacy-preserving noise, EPPS-DMLCA achieves higher accuracy than FedAvg-DP and Drynx.
- **Scalability:** the experimental results show that the model is scaled, as evidenced by its significantly reduced run time when the number of cloud servers is enhanced. EPPS-DMLCA is an efficient and reliable solution for distributed, on-demand federated learning. It can be used to perform large-scale applications securely in areas where healthcare and bank sectors and other transactional institutions retain their clients' information.

Compared to other modern frameworks, it can be seen that, on the one hand, FedAvg-DP has no strong privacy guarantees due to low computational overhead in the face of collaborative attacks. On the other hand, Drynx can boast resistance to such privacy issues

brought on by the collusion attack, as it combines secure multiparty computation and differential privacy. However, despite the robust privacy properties of Drynx, the computational costs associated with such a framework are too high, and the introduced differential privacy results in a lower model utility. Thus, the newly developed privacy-preserving distributed machine learning approach EPPS-DMLCA is superior to the existing ones, as it ensures better privacy protection and is more efficient, secure, and scalable than the rest of the frameworks.

Future Work

Optimization of Noise Levels

One of the primary challenges in the differential privacy methods is formalizing how privacy degrades concerning utility. Future work focuses on optimizing the noise levels injected to achieve differential privacy and maintain good utility for industrial applications, such as speech recognition, medical diagnosis, etc. One potential direction is to calibrate the noise levels adaptively depending on the sensitivity of the data.

Support for high-dimensional Data

While this paper has evaluated EPPS-DMLCA focusing on the hand-written digit dataset, i.e., MNIST, which is relatively low-dimensional, future works should study the case when the high-dimensional data, such as genomics, medical imaging, and NLP, is used. Ensuring that high-dimensional data encryption and noise applications work appropriately would be challenging.

Multi-Cloud and Cross-Cloud Architectures

Extending the EPPS-DMLCA framework to multi-cloud and cross-cloud infrastructures would be fruitful. In this multi-cloud architecture, data storage and computations occur with multiple clouds. In cross-cloud architecture, data and computations reside between different clouds, and each cloud has its way of maintaining security and privacy.

Real-World Implementation and Deployment

Future work should focus on deploying EPPS-DMLCA into natural industrial systems, e.g., healthcare, financial transactions, and smart grids. While this paper has evaluated the implementation in a research environment, medical data, financial transactions, and social media data are more dynamic, require real-time data updates, and are very sensitive. They require the deployment of EPPS-DMLCA in practice and must also provide fault tolerance because some data may be lost over time, and data sources are varied.

Integration with Advanced Machine Learning Model

The same architecture has been used for a CNN model in this paper. In this study, the future work that must be included in further EPPS-DMLCA is integrating the applied method into advanced machine learning methods: DNN, RNN, and Transformer. It should be integrated into widely used tasks: speech recognition, image captioning, and language models.

6.2.6 Energy Efficiency of EPPS-DMLCA
Finally, as the computation and data volume of the AWS cloud continuously increases, the energy consumed also increases. Thus, it would be helpful to devise a way to maintain the efficiency and effectiveness of EPPS-DMLCA while minimizing the energy consumed using the same amount of computation. Future work should research this by, for instance, developing a new way of encryption or fully utilizing the properties of currently available low-power devices.

Resilience to emerging attacks and risks

Another endpoint of the future work for EPPS-DMLCA is ensuring it remains secure against all possible attacks. With the advent of new classes of threats from quantum computing, it should be researched how to integrate homomorphic encryption with quantum-resistant cryptography.

Practical Implications

The EPPS-DMLCA framework has tremendous implications in many fields where safety and privacy are vital. In the healthcare industry, for example, the EPPS-DMLCA can train models safely without exposing the patients' information. Yet, it enables data from multiple hospitals to be included in one safe database without interference with the privacy of client data. The same is the case in the finance industry. Here, firms capable of leveraging EPPS-DMLCA can safely analyze bank clients' data and avoid fraud by analyzing clients' transactions across the different banks they engage in while still adhering to the privacy of the client's data.

Today's world has a string of laws with which all data analytical frameworks must comply. Examples of such data privacy laws are the GDPR in Europe and the CCPA in California. EPPS-DMLCA is the first framework that allows machine learning to be conducted on the analyzed data in an encrypted module while ensuring the implicated company adheres to the data privacy regulations prevalent in the region. As such, EPPS-DMLCA offers a valuable tool for companies that want to adhere to specific data protection privacy laws yet still access the massive power held in the machine learning data.

Final Remarks

In conclusion, EPPS-DMLCA represents a highly effective, transparent, and secure approach to privacy-preserving distributed machine learning. As the framework in question reduces the impact of the identity disclosure approach and its vulnerability to collusion attacks, it will be seen as the foundation for new techniques used in various industries. In other words, with further research, the framework can serve as a cornerstone for privacy-preserving AI in big data and cloud computing.

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